

Synergizing Fuzzy-based Task Offloading with Machine Learning-driven Forecasting for IoT

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Abstract—Nowadays IoT applications play an increasing role in our lives, which require adaptive solutions to meet an acceptable level of quality. To support this need, IoT is often coupled with fog and cloud services, especially for real-time applications, where short latency and fast data integration matter the most. To manage such IoT-Fog-Cloud systems effectively, task offloading methods are needed, which represent an NP-hard problem, to be addressed by scheduling algorithms using some sort of heuristics. In this paper, we present a fuzzy-based offloading algorithm improved by machine learning-based time-series prediction to boost its decision making, and thus to reach efficient system usage. We also extend and use the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator to evaluate our proposed approach on a real-world-based IoT use case. Our results showed improvements by reducing execution time of the considered IoT application with essentially the same utilisation cost, energy consumption and network usage.

Index Terms—Machine Learning, Prediction, Task Offloading, Fog Computing, Simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Distributed architectures such as Edge and Fog Computing (EC, FC) are often associated with Internet of Things (IoT), in order to process and store data of modern applications. To avoid overloaded communication channels and resources, Cloud Computing (CC) is improved towards FC by introducing resource-constrained nodes close to end-users to offload cloud resources and reduce the latency between the end-devices and computing nodes [2]. IoT intends to improve all parts of our lives, hence IoT applications typically use smart devices, sensors, and actuators to introduce novel concepts and procedures to various fields: IoT Healthcare, Industry 4.0 and Smart Cities. Since IoT devices can exceed hundreds of thousands in number, vast amounts of data should be controlled carefully, therefore the appropriate computing capacity and latency are decisive for time-critical applications.

To mitigate resource-constrained computing nodes, offloading strategies are often applied, which decide where to execute each task to optimise various objectives, typically execution cost, energy consumption and system performance [3]. To solve the task offloading problem, which is known to be NP-hard, various optimisation techniques, such as machine learning-based (ML) algorithms or multi-objective optimisation, are applied to relieve the computing nodes more effectively. To facilitate the operation of complex IoT applications,

prediction methods are also utilised to gain information about future events and thus, to improve Quality of Service (QoS) and predict possible failures [4]. To forecast the anticipated load for the computing nodes, historical data are involved for time series analysis, typically originating from IoT sensors or other participants of the concrete system.

In this paper, we combine the aforementioned areas, namely task offloading and data volume prediction, to design an ML-assisted task offloading algorithm, which supports effective utilisation of IoT-Fog-Cloud systems. We also design a fuzzy-based optimisation method by involving forecasting as one of the objectives of the algorithm. The challenge of our work is to establish a framework, which is able to handle the complex model of the Cloud-to-Thing Continuum, and which is applicable to investigate how the ML-based predictors and fuzzy logic can interact. For our research, we chose the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator due to its performance and reliability [10] to evaluate our proposed algorithms with a real-life IoT use case.

The remainder of the work is arranged as follows: Section II provides background information and reviews related work. The details of the design and implementation of our proposed methods are described in Section III. The results of the experiment are shown and discussed in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines future work.

II. RELATED WORKS

Mahdavinejad et al. [7] presents a survey on the frequently utilised machine learning algorithms for IoT data analysis, which are exploited by various applications aiming at weather, energy consumption, traffic or travel pattern prediction. To deal with time series and sequential data, Markov models, sliding-window methods, and recurrent neural networks are also recommended.

In [6], air quality data is monitored by using real gas, temperature, and humidity IoT sensors, then the acquired data are also used for time series analysis applying Linear Regression (LR) to predict the air quality index of the following days. Another real-world example for the prediction of IoT data is presented in [8], where the pressure, vibration, and other parameters of a power station are measured with various sensors. To avoid/detect anomaly or critical error, time series

TABLE I: Comparison of some related approaches.

Work	Task Offloading	Prediction	Method	Considered Parameters	Environment
[6]	-	X	LR	Air quality index	Real devices
[8]	-	X	LSTM, ARIMA	Working conditions of the power station	Real devices
[4]	-	X	ARIMA	Sensors of a slitting machine	Real devices
[21]	-	X	LSTM	CPU, Memory Bandwidth, Node position in the topology	iFogSim
[5]	X	-	Fuzzy logic	Local topology, Actual load Utilisation cost, Unprocessed data	DISSECT-CF-Fog
[12]	X	-	Fuzzy logic	Task size, Node's VM Utilisation Network delay, Neighbors' VM utilisation Bandwidth	EdgeCloudSim
[19]	X	-	Fuzzy logic	Community price, Required resource Task priority, Unprocessed data	iFogSim
[18]	X	X	Fuzzy logic with LR and SVR	Cost, Response time Workload	iFogSim
<i>This proposal</i>	X	X	Fuzzy logic with 6 predictors	Local topology, Actual load Utilisation cost, Amount of unprocessed data Predicted unprocessed data	DISSECT-CF-Fog

analysis involving the historical data of the sensors are applied, the authors consider the neural network-based Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and the AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model for such purposes. Another real-life example of the usage of ARIMA presented in [4], the input of the model is collected from various sensors of a slitting machine to predict quality defects in manufacturing.

Wang et al. [3] discuss the challenges and classification of task offloading. Due to the complexity of IoT-Fog-Cloud systems, it is hard to find an optimal solution to determine to which nodes the tasks should be assigned to be processed. In this decision not just various objectives (e.g. response time, cost), but the type of the task (i.e. independent or workflow-like task), the type of the offloading (i.e. the task should be fully offloaded or just partially) or the mobility of IoT devices they (are able to move from one location to another, which can easily degrade the QoS) are usually inspected.

In [21], a solution based on proactive prediction of insufficient resources was introduced that reduces the outage of fog node resources, which utilises the LSTM network. The method takes into account the probability of failure which denotes when the resources of computation, storage, and bandwidth are inadequate during a certain time period.

Fuzzy theory is a widely used technique in computer science; thus it also demands space in FC to help stakeholders to make a better decision. Fuzzy logic transforms the *true or false* decision into *degrees of truth* [11] involving selection, prioritisation, and observation of different actions. In [12], the authors propose a fuzzy decision-based task offloading management framework for EC and CC. To overcome the issue of resource-constrained computing nodes, a centralised

orchestrator management layer is introduced, as a decision maker gathering all available information: actual load and resources of the computing nodes, network properties and size and amount of tasks.

Earlier, we proposed a task and resource management algorithm for IoT-Fog-Cloud systems based on Pliant logic [5], which is a kind of fuzzy system. In that work, each node is able to make a decision separately, to which adjacent node the task should be forwarded to. This decentralised manner helps to get rid of the less relevant information and saves time and network usage during the decision making. The considered method builds on the local topology (i.e. neighbour and parent nodes), the actual load, the utilisation cost, and the actual amount of unprocessed data. The shortcomings of that earlier work are that only the current state of the system is involved when a decision is made, and it lacks historical information to foster decision-making.

A. ML-based predictors

In [18], a fuzzy-based approach is proposed to balance local processing at the edge of the network. The authors also use the combination of Linear Regression (LR) and Support Vector Regression (SVR) to predict the future values including cost and response time and future workload prediction. Then the fuzzy self-learning algorithm was applied to how to scale up/down the resources. Another approach [19] uses the fuzzy system for a Vehicular Fog Computing architecture, to maximise profits and to meet the deadline of the tasks by offloading tasks to fog vehicles, which were offered to be used for the community in exchange for profit.

Fig. 1: The prediction UI with the available configurations, the forecasting and error metrics.

Although time series forecasting is a strong weapon for learning patterns and thus predicting unforeseen size of data/tasks in the future, unexpected events may still occur. IoT is ubiquitous and elastic, and its use cases are diverse, thus the entities participating in it can join and leave the system unpredictably. Furthermore, due to the multi-layered characteristics of Fog-Cloud systems, data is not just produced at the lowest level (i.e., IoT layer), but task migrations among computing nodes in the upper layers occur, which should also be predicted in an effective manner. As a consequence, relying only on the feedback of time series analysis can cause drawbacks in the management of IoT-Fog-Cloud systems. As a result, in this paper, we propose a novel approach by combining time series analysis with our Fuzzy-based Pliant data offloading algorithm, in order to handle the above mentioned complexity of IoT-Fog-Cloud systems. Furthermore, our method offers more predictors for time series analysis, than the previously existing solutions.

III. THE PROPOSED ML-ASSISTED FRAMEWORK

In this section, we present the novel extension of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator¹, which is able to take into account data volume forecasting in the offloading decision. The simulation tool is a general-purpose, discrete-event simulator with diverse abilities including but not limited to simulation of physical machines, virtual machines, IoT devices, and applications with the related measurement functions of the components' energy, cost, and network usage. The simulator's decentralised decision-makers, which determine to which adjacent node the task should be reassigned to, are able to deal with naive approaches, as described below.

The *Hold Down* strategy only considers neighbours and omits the parent node, thus it keeps the tasks in a fog layer as low as possible. Meanwhile, *Push Up* omits the neighbours

and always sends the data to upper layers. These strategies leverage one of the trade-offs of a multi-layered fog topology: the higher layer a task is processed, the stronger resources can be utilised to get faster processing as well. However, the lower layer a task is processed, the less computational cost can be expected since weaker resources are sold cheaper.

A more sophisticated strategy, namely *Pliant*, has also been developed in [5]. Here, for each reachable fog and cloud node we calculate a score. The first step is data normalisation to the [0,1] interval with a Sigmoid function, which is one of the most popular threshold functions. If the normalised value is close to 1 that means that it is a more valuable property. We might want to modify the importance of the value. If this value is greater or smaller than our expectation, we use the Kappa function [22] for such a purpose, which is also a Sigmoid-like function. The next step is to merge these values applying different kinds of operators in continuous value logic: conjunctive, disjunctive, and aggregative. Finally, the score value is rounded to an integer number that represents the probability of the different alternative nodes. Using these score values as probabilities for each node, we randomly choose the one where the task will be migrated.

To make time series analysis available in the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, we used the *Scikit-learn* library, which provides various data analysis methods, and ML-algorithms. *Tensorflow* was also involved, which is a framework for machine learning and artificial intelligence and used to train and deduce a deep neural network.

The proposed predictor framework has a user-friendly interface as shown in Figure 1, which can be used to set the necessary parameters for the time series analysis. To add the predicted parameters to the Pliant algorithm during decision making, we first need data pre-processing. The original data is denoted with grey colour in Figure 1's diagram. This step is necessary because ML and neural network models can more easily learn the characteristics and patterns of the data, if they

¹<https://github.com/sed-inf-u-szeged/DISSECT-CF-Fog> (accessed on 17.10.2023)

are uniform and placed between a certain interval, thus we *normalise* the data to the [0,1] interval. We can also observe that the data follow a stepwise pattern. Usually it is difficult to create a predictor for such a pattern, thus we used one of the well-known smoothing techniques called the Savitzky-Golay method [20]. This procedure goes through the dataset using a window with a given width, then an n -degree polynomial fit is performed at the centre of each window. As a result of preprocessing, the data series are simpler with minimal noise, but the main features and patterns remain.

To predict the possible future value of a feature, the simulator waits for the predefined number of measurements (e.g. 256 input values to the prediction). In this case, the red line in the diagram in Figure 1 denotes the size of the not yet processed data for each computing node. When the required amount of samples is available, the 256-length list is divided into a training and test dataset at a ratio of 0.75-0.25% (as shown with dashed vertical lines in Figure 1). Whenever the measurement-list is updated, the earliest information is removed from the list (i.e. it follows the FIFO-logic), thus in every iteration, the training and test database are also updated accordingly. To measure how accurately a predictor forecast the test data based on the training data, which denoted with blue in Figure 1, we applied the following error metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

Then on the full 256-length dataset, the predictor makes a forecasting again, and the predicted future values with the formerly measured error metrics are forwarded to the Pliant-based decision maker, which can decide how reliable the forecasting really is. The results of the actual 64-length predictions are visually represented with pink in Figure 1 with the actual error metrics, which are the outputs of the prediction. The amount of the not yet processed data (i.e. unprocessed data) is predicted for each computing node separately. In the predictor framework, we implemented six different kinds of prediction algorithm which are the following:

The three-component ARIMA [13] is a statistical model and is a type of regression analysis to predict the upcoming points of a series, which comes with three input parameters. Component AR with parameter p represents the order of autoregression, which is the number of lagged observations to be used (lag is a fixed amount of passing time). To use ARIMA more effectively, module I with parameter d makes the time series stationary, which means that the mean and variance of the series remain constant. The difference between the data values and the previous values is taken d -times until the original series becomes stationary. Finally, component MA with parameter q is the moving average, it denotes the correlation between the current value of the time series and past forecasting errors. q is the size of the moving average window.

Another popular procedure to foresee is the Holt-Winter's (HW) Method [14], which is able to consider the average, trends, and seasonality of the dataset, because it is not a standalone method, but the combination of three: Simple

Exponential Smoothing (SES), Holt's Exponential Smoothing (HES) and Winter's Exponential Smoothing (WES). SES is only ideal if the data contain no seasonality and trends, because this part only focuses on the average of recent periods. It comes with the parameter α , which is the smoothing coefficient between 0 and 1. If the value is close to 1, it means the more recent members of the series are taken into account, otherwise it is close to zero, then it means a more history-based prediction. HES involves the trend components, which is the long-term changing of the data (i.e. a slope), its parameter called β , and it is an additional smoothing factor. Last but not least, WES takes into account the seasonality of the data, which reflects a cyclical repeating pattern. It comes with the parameter γ , and similarly it is responsible for smoothing of the seasonal component. This component also requires a parameter $period$ that is actually just the length of the historical data which we take for seasonality. These three parameters are combined to be called the HW Method. Two more parameters are needed, called $type$ both for trend and seasonality, which can be set to additive or multiplicative, depending on whether the trend and the seasonality are linear or exponential, respectively. The additive means that all variables in the time series are simply summed to produce a forecast. In the multiplicative model instead of addition, multiplication is used to forecast.

Random Forest (RF) [15] is an ensemble of decision trees to generate the predicted value of series. The first parameter is the *number of trees*, which are independent, and the data distributed for each tree is selected randomly from the dataset. The next step is decision making, where each decision tree makes an individual decision based on the input data. The last step is aggregation, where we calculate an average value based on the results of the decision trees to get the predicted values. The RF also comes with the parameter lag to reflect the length of the historical data and the parameter $depth$, which controls the size of the tree to avoid overfitting.

Linear Regression (LR) [16] is a simple way to predict future values, it assumes a linear relationship between the data to be predicted and the already available data, thus it plots a line by minimising squared error between them.

Support Vector Regression (SVR) [17] is based on a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification algorithm, but can also be applied to regression tasks. The SVM method is used to find a hyperplane for a classification task, which separates the training data into classes. With SVR, the concept is very similar, but here we are looking for a hypersurface on which the training data fits the best. SVR can also handle non-linear data using a kernel function, namely RBF (Gaussian), Sigmoid or Polynomial, which maps the training data to a higher dimension.

Finally, we also implemented a neural network-based solution, the LSTM [9], which is dedicated for time series analysis. LSTM is capable of remembering long time series easily, whilst other neural networks can only remember short-term information. LSTM is based on RNN. An LSTM neural network is made up of specially designed cells, each cell has

Fig. 2: The flow of the simulation including AI-based decision making and prediction.

gates called forget, input and output gates, which decide what should happen with the information under processing. The LSTM cells have an internal state that carries the information. This state can be modified by the gates, for instance, they can modify, add or take away information from it. The decision, which information to leave from the cell state, is decided by the forget gate. The input gate is responsible for what new information to add to the state. Finally, the output gate, which is responsible for the internal state of the cell, decides which information to add from the state to the next LSTM cell. In our implementation, the following parameters are required by the LSTM network: the *loss function* is used for training, and is reduced by the model during the training process. Furthermore, *batch size* to determine the number of samples to deal with before updating the parameters of the model, and the *epoch size* to define how many times the learning algorithm works through the full training set are also needed. The size of the LSTM is determined by the *number of layers*, the *cells in a layer*, the *size of the input*, which are the amount of the lagged data, and *size of the output*, which is the amount of the prediction length. The *dropout* value is used to prevent overfitting, by defining the rate of randomly selected LSTM cells to be forgotten. Lastly, it also needs an *activation function* to decide whether the cells' value is important or not in the process, and an *Optimisation algorithm* that is used to update weights and biases.

A. The Offloading Mechanisms

The flow of the proposed simulation extension can be seen in Figure 2, which consists of five steps. It is worth mentioning that these steps are executed by each IoT device and computing node separately; *Step 1* is for devices, whilst *Step 2-5* are for nodes.

In *Step 1*, each IoT device produces data according to its predefined settings, which includes the size of measured data, the lifetime of a device and the data sampling interval. The produced data are forwarded to one of the fog nodes. On the computing nodes, either fog or cloud, tasks are formed from

the incoming data in *Step 2*, and for each task a given amount of instructions (i.e. the length of the task, which is based on the amount of data to be processed) are also associated to simulate the utilisation of resources. In *Step 3*, each node starts collecting those features, which are involved in the time series analysis (i.e. the not yet processed data).

To avoid the overhead of the offloading mechanism, our offloading mechanism works in a decentralised manner, therefore each node triggers the decision making algorithm, if the ratio of the not yet processed data and the maximum amount of bytes that a task can represent are greater than their predefined values in *Step 4*. This step contains Sub-step 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4 as well. In this paper, our decision makers execute partial offloading, however it can be easily modified during the configuration of the simulation to work with fully offloaded tasks. During the decision making process, various decision makers can be involved, as described earlier in Section III. In the case of the Pliant algorithm, we also take into account the time series analysis, where the data collected in *Step 3* are used. Finally, in addition to tasks that are ready to be assigned to a virtual machine to be processed, the rest of the tasks are forwarded based on the output of the decision maker algorithm in *Step 5*. Besides that, a daemon service keeps scaling up and down the number of virtual machines for each node according to the actual load.

By default, the size of the prediction length is 64. When the Pliant algorithm takes into account the possibility of using the predicted value, it can decide how exactly the predicted values are being involved in the decision making. For example, the decision maker can use values from the near future, or the far future or it can combine them as well. In this paper, we use the average of near future values, because these values are usually more accurate.

Our previous experience with Pliant strategy was effective, when we used the following properties to construct the score value for each node: actual load of the resources, utilisation cost and unprocessed data. As we mentioned before, the score

value indicates how seemingly good the decision is, so the higher value the algorithm gives, the more preferably the node is. In this work, we extend the score calculation of the algorithm with the predicted value with its error metrics to compare it to the actual unprocessed data. If the forecast value is less, than the unprocessed data then the algorithm gives a strong value (close to 1), because it means that the node is not supposed to get too much data in the future.

IV. EVALUATION

Fig. 3: The multi-layered IoT-Fog-Cloud system positioned in Hungary with 20 devices.

To measure the effectiveness and the differences of our offloading algorithms extended with various predictors, we evaluated a real-world IoT scenario with the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, which were inspired by and operated based on an existing meteorological service (<https://idokep.hu>), where weather stations measure the atmosphere; its temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction, and so on. To be as realistic as possible, we positioned the fog and cloud nodes in Hungarian cities, and the location of IoT devices is also positioned nearby them, as depicted in Figure 3. In this example, only 20 IoT devices are shown, but during the evaluation we scaled up the number of active devices to 2000, and then to 4000.

Furthermore, during the five-hour long simulation, these devices work periodically, as follows. In the first hour, only two devices run, then we scale the number of devices up to six until the end of the second hour. In the next hour, only three devices, whilst in the fourth hour seven devices are operated. In the last, fifth hour we return to the original state, thus only two devices generate load for computing nodes. To evaluate this periodic behaviour of IoT devices on larger-scale as well, we are able to evenly scale up the number of devices running in every hour. To represent realistic communication delay between a device and a computing node, the average 4G latency (50 ms) is applied, plus it is weighted proportionally to the Euclidean distance.

To avoid the bottleneck-effect of the cloud data centre in case of high amount of IoT devices, we also applied clustering in the multi-layered fog topology: in Figure 3, *fog1* suffix

TABLE II: Parameters used for the simulation evaluation.

Parameters		Value
Offloading strategy	Task forwarding ratio	0.9
	Partial offloading (%)	50
	Pliant future values (pc.)	10
Device settings	Scaling multiplier	100, 200
	Base latency (ms)	50
	Data generation freq. (min.)	1
	Data size (byte)	150
Processing settings	Max. task size (kByte)	5
	Max. task length (min.)	4
Prediction configuration	Prediction length	64
	Test size	64
	Batch size	256
	Smoothing window size	48
	Smoothing polynomial degree	5
ARIMA	p, q, d	3, 0, 0
HW	Trend and Seasonal type	<i>Add</i>
	Alpha, Beta, Gamma	0.1
	Seasonal period	60
RF	Number of trees	10
	Max. depth	50
	Lags	100
LR	-	-
SVR	Kernel	<i>RBF</i>
	Loss function	<i>MSE</i>
LSTM	Epoch size	25
	Batch size	32
	Number of layers	4
	Cells in a layer	50
	Size of the input	256
	Size of the output	60
	Dropout	0.2
	Activation function	<i>Tanh, Sigmoid</i>
	Optimisation algorithm	<i>Adam</i>

denotes fog nodes having the weakest computing power (16 CPU cores and 32 GB RAM), *fog2* means the fog cluster head (32 CPU cores, 64 GB RAM), and finally, there is only one *_cloud* with 520 CPU cores and 7680 GB RAM. The capacity of the cloud node mimics the ELKH Cloud schema [1]. Figure 3 also presents the connections among the computing nodes (green lines) and the communication delay (i.e. latency) in ms (blue numbers), these connections determine where an overloaded node can forward the tasks to, in case of the offloading algorithm triggering. As it is also clearly seen in the figure that certain territories are not covered equally by the computing nodes (e.g. the area of Lake Balaton), which challenges the offloading algorithm.

Different layers deal with different kinds of virtual machines, which were configured to work as instances of the AWS EC2 service. For example, VMs running on the cloud node require 8 CPU and 16 GB RAM (similarly as the *a1.2xlarge* instance does for 0.204\$ per hour). *fog1* nodes run with 4 CPU and 8 GB RAM for 0.102\$ hourly, and finally *fog2* halves the required resources, this it deals with 2 CPU and 4 GB RAM for 0.051\$ hourly price.

The parameters, used for the simulation and for the prediction as well, are summarised in Table II. It shows that an

TABLE III: Results of the simulation evaluation with 2000 IoT devices.

Scaling multiplier	100								
Offloading strategy	Pliant	ARIMA	HW	Pliant with		SVR	LSTM	Push Up	Hold Down
				RF	LR				
Timeout (min.)	9	6	7	6	5	8	8	5	16
Runtime (sec.)	7	139	29	113	9	12	58	4	4
Node Energy (kWh)	42.4430	42.3919	42.4983	42.3664	42.2998	42.4214	42.3227	40.942	42.8018
Utilisation Cost (\$)	22.4399	22.4323	22.4340	22.3779	22.3983	22.4425	22.4255	24.1774	17.7956
Time on the Network (sec.)	46	46	46	46	46	47	46	39	84
Data on the Network (MB)	36	36	36	36	36	36	36	20	141
Number of VMs	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	63
Number of Tasks	3656	3653	3658	3659	3659	3650	3652	3623	3584
Number of Predictions	-	414	428	420	416	418	443	-	-
Average Error of Predictions	-	0.223	1.056	0.235	0.264	0.359	0.201	-	-

TABLE IV: Results of the simulation evaluation 4000 IoT devices.

Scaling multiplier	200								
Offloading strategy	Pliant	ARIMA	HW	Pliant with		SVR	LSTM	Push Up	Hold Down
				RF	LR				
Timeout (min.)	101	94	99	98	98	97	101	243	421
Runtime (sec.)	11	276	35	130	13	16	60	7	7
Node Energy (kWh)	52.2389	51.7500	52.0986	52.0569	51.9911	52.0054	52.2093	62.0515	52.2643
Utilisation Cost (\$)	41.5038	41.3116	41.4434	41.4137	41.4120	41.4051	41.4732	45.8719	34.5227
Time on the Network (sec.)	58	59	58	59	58	59	58	52	149
Data on the Network (MB)	126	125	126	126	126	126	125	47	2457
Number of VMs	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	82	63
Number of Tasks	7049	7061	7051	7051	7052	7053	7055	7047	7008
Number of Predictions	-	439	457	452	455	482	442	-	-
Average Error of Predictions	-	0.233	0.635	0.251	0.216	0.311	0.235	-	-

evaluation has numerous input variables, and their changes are able to effect the results. Therefore, in this work, we rather focused on synergizing the Fuzzy-based task offloading with the predictors in the simulation framework, and fixed the parameters as close as possible to a real cloud provider (ELKH Cloud) and meteorological service (*idokep.hu*).

These values were applied for two scenarios, first 2000 IoT devices utilised the computing architecture, then we doubled the number of active devices, thus 4000 IoT devices were operating. For each scenario, we applied 9 different offloading algorithms. The greedy *Push Up* and *Hold Down*, and then the *Pliant* strategy were considered as baselines, and to compare these to the extended, ML-assisted *Pliant* strategy. The LSTM network was trained using the results of the *Pliant* strategy with the 5 predictors added separately.

A. Results

The evaluation results of the proposed ML-assisted task offloading algorithm are shown in Table III and Table IV. In each row, the blue background indicates the smallest, the red background denotes the largest value, if it exists. For the comparison, we take into account the following outputs of the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulation environment: the *Timeout* value measures how much time is needed after the last IoT data fragment is forwarded to a computing node to be processed. A less effective configuration of the offloading mechanism may

cause data congestion, therefore the less the *Timeout* is, the more real-time the application is. The *Runtime* measures how long the simulation runs on the host machine. In this paper, the measurements were conducted using a PC equipped with Intel Core i7-3770 CPU @ 3.40GHz, 23 GB RAM and Ubuntu 20.04 operation systems.

Node Energy reflects the total energy consumption of the computing nodes (calculated based on the ELKH Cloud properties). *Utilisation Cost* was collected depending on the used AWS VM instances. These two characteristics of the simulation results are highly influenced by the offloading algorithm. As we mentioned before, the stronger VM instance a task utilised, the more energy is consumed and the more fee we must pay for it, therefore it matters how wisely the offloading algorithm chose. *Time on the Network* and *Data on the Network* also depend on the offloading decisions, they measure how much data was forwarded between the computing nodes all together, and how much time it took.

Finally, some statistical values are also available from the output, how many virtual machines were needed to process all data (*Number of VMs*), how many tasks were created based on that data (*Number of Tasks*), how many times the prediction algorithm was triggered during the evaluation (*Number of Predictions*), and finally, how large the average error of the three error metrics (MAE, MSE, RMSE) for each predictor

was (*Average error of Predictions*).

As the results show, in many cases the *Push Up* and *Hold Down* strategies mean the upper and lower bounds. However, as Table III presents, the same execution time can be achieved (*Timeout* = 5) by applying the *Pliant with LR* algorithm for almost 2\$ cheaper. During the second scenario, as it is shown in Figure IV, the *Pliant with ARIMA* strategy managed the task processing more efficiently from the aspect of execution time (*Timeout* = 94), however it can be clearly seen that in the second scenario, due to the amount of IoT devices and their data, the computing nodes became overloaded. Nevertheless, in both evaluation cases (with 2000 and 4000 IoT devices), the *Pliant with LR / ARIMA* successfully reduced the execution time of the application, with fair usage of energy and costs.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a novel simulation framework extension for the DISSECT-CF-Fog simulator, which utilises six ML predictor methods for time series analysis to predict the future value of the incoming data for each computing node. The gained information was then used in the fuzzy-based Pliant algorithm, besides further features of the system. To the best of our knowledge, a similar combination of such methods has never been used in a simulation environment so far. Based on the evaluation results, we have shown that complex IoT-Fog-Cloud systems require sophisticated decisions to work efficiently, due to their versatile nature. There is no universally good solution, however extending our Pliant algorithm with predictors can achieve faster execution time compared to the baselines strategies. During the evaluation, our algorithm always took into account the result of only one predictor for the prediction of yet unprocessed data. In the future, we plan to further extend our environment for fine-tuning of the prediction parameters, and to involve as many predicted future values for as many available features as needed, for the optimal management of IoT use cases.

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